

FUNCTIONALIZED HIGH-K NANOWIRES POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES WITH ENHANCED ENERGY STORAGE CAPABILITY

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ABSTRACT

Materials with high energy density, easy-processing, and great flexibility are highly desired due to the rapid development of electrical energy storage devices. Therefore, high dielectric constant (high-k) polymer nanocomposites, which possessing three advantages mentioned above, have received numerous attention. However, introducing high-k ceramics into polymer matrix often damage the breakdown strength of polymer matrix, which is crucial for energy storage capability. Here, bio-inspired fluoropolydopamine modified BaTiO₃ nanowires (NWs) was introduced into fluoropolymer matrix to enhance the energy density of polymer matrix, resulting enhanced dielectric constant and comparative breakdown strength. At an electric field of 480 kV/mm, nanocomposite containing 5 vol % modified BaTiO₃ NWs exhibits an ultrahigh energy density of 12.87 J cm⁻³, which is more than three and a half times of biaxial-oriented polypropylene (BOPP, 3.56 J cm⁻³ at 600 kV/mm). This strategy paves a new way to fabricating high energy storage polymer nanocomposites.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the past few decades, miniaturization of electronic devices induce plenty of attention on fabricating high energy storage polymer-based dielectrics.¹⁻³ With respect to the low dielectric constant (2.2 at 1 kHz) of biaxial-oriented polypropylene (BOPP), which is the commercial polymer film capacitor, its low energy density restricts its application in future electronics. Therefore, polymer-based nanocomposites with high-k nanofillers are extensively explored to manufacturing high energy density materials.⁴⁻⁶ Poly(vinylidene fluoride)(PVDF), its copolymers and terpolymers have drawn tremendous attention because of its high dielectric constant and breakdown strength.⁴⁻⁶ Comparing with nanoparticles, one-dimensional (1D) high-k nanofillers show greater impact on enhancing the dielectric constant of polymer matrix, which is critical for improving energy storage property of polymer matrix.⁷⁻⁸ In the mean time, the 1D high-k nanofillers might weaken its poor dispersity in polymer matrix due to its lower specific surface.⁹⁻¹⁰ Nevertheless, the enhancement of permittivity often accompanied by the decrease of breakdown strength of polymer matrix, which is harmful to improvement of energy storage property. As a consequence, introducing high-k nanofillers into polymer matrix might be significant for energy storage improvement to settle this contradiction.

Surface modification is an effective method to mitigate the contradiction of improving the permittivity of polymer matrix while maintaining the breakdown strength by incorporating high-k nanofillers into polymer matrix.¹¹⁻¹³ During the past few decades, a series of methods have been applied to functionalize nanofillers, such as layer-by-layer assembly,¹⁴ “grafting from”, and “grafting to” strategy.¹⁵⁻¹⁷ However, these conventional ways are either time-consuming or material depending. In recent years, polydopamine (PDA) has gained vast attention because of its great adhesion capability on any substrates.¹⁸⁻²⁰ Lately, lots of work have been conducted to mitigate the dispersion issue of nanofillers in polymer matrix to fabricating high energy density polymer nanocomposites.²¹⁻²² Nevertheless, compared to those conventional strategy of surface modification, the application of dopamine upon the functionalization of nanofillers is still at the primary moment.

Herein, with the purpose of uncovering the prospect of PDA modification and enhancing the homogeneity of nanofillers in polymer matrix, a fluoro-dopamine derivative is conducted to modify BaTiO₃ NWs to improve the energy storage property of fluoro-polymer matrix. By fixing finely designed long fluoro-chain to dopamine, the as-modified fluoro-polydopamine paves a new way to

better incorporating BaTiO₃ NWs into fluoro-polymer matrix. The fluoro-polymer nanocomposite containing 2.5 vol % and 5 vol % functionalized BaTiO₃ NWs exhibit ultrahigh discharged energy densities of 12.68 J·cm⁻³ and 12.87 J·cm⁻³, respectively, which is far more beyond the commercial BOPP (3.56 J·cm⁻³ at 600 kV/mm).²⁰ Compared with traditional cumbersome strategies, our simple and efficient method comes out to be promising to meet the development of polymer nanocomposites for energy storage applications.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Materials

Poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropylene) (P(VDF-HFP)) containing 15% HFP was kindly provided by Solvay Plastics (Shanghai, China). Titanium dioxide (TiO₂, ≥99.5%) and 1H, 1H, 2H, 2H-perfluoro-1-decanol (TCI, 96%) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and Tansoole (China), respectively. p-toluenesulfonic acid and 3, 4-dihydroxy-L-phenylalanine (L-DOPA, 99%) monohydrate (98%) were purchased from Aladdin (China). Other reagents were purchased from Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd. (China) and Tansoole (China).

2.2 Synthesis of 1H,1H,2H,2H-heptadecafluorodecyl 2-amino-3-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)propanoate (f-DOPA)

A mixture of L-DOPA (3.94 g, 20 mmol), 1H,1H,2H,2H-perfluoro-1-decanol (9.28 g, 20 mmol), and p-toluenesulfonic acid monohydrate (3.80 g, 20 mmol) was added into 250 mL flask containing 100 mL toluene. Then the suspension was reflux under N₂ atmosphere for 48 h, along with a Dean-Stark trap to remove water. After cooling down, the mixture was rotary evaporated under vacuum to remove toluene. The gel-like residue was then washed with saturated NaHCO₃ aqueous solution and subsequently extracted with ethyl acetate. Afterwards, the solution was washed with brine for a few times. Then the solution was dried over anhydrous MgSO₄ and separated by filtration. The product was obtained by recrystallized the filter cake from petroleum ether several times. Yield: 8.17 g, colorless solid (63.52 %).

2.3 Surface Modification of Nanowires

The BaTiO₃ NWs were synthesized by a multi-step hydrothermal reaction described in our previous work.²³ Then, the synthesized f-DOPA were employed to functionalize the pristine BaTiO₃ NWs. In a typical procedure, 3g BaTiO₃ NWs were added into 80 mL Tris-HCl buffered solution (pH = 8.5) and ultrasonic processed for 1 h. On the other hand, 4 mmol f-DOPA was mixed in 40 mL 2-propanol. Then, the obtained f-DOPA solution was added dropwise into the above-mentioned BaTiO₃ NWs solution under severe stirring at 60 °C. After stirring for another 48h, the solid residue were washed with deionized water several times to remove the unreacted f-DOPA. These received solid were named as f-DOPA@BaTiO₃.

2.4 Fabrication of P(VDF-HFP)-based Nanocomposite Films

Those f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs were added into N, N-dimethylformamide by ultrasonication for 1 h. After the addition of certain amount of P(VDF-HFP), the hybrid solution was then stirred vigorously under ambient temperature for another 24 h. Then the solution was casted on a glass plate with a scraper at certain thickness. After being dried in vacuum at 40 °C for 12 h, the as-prepared films were heated at 200 °C for seven minutes and then quenched into ice water immediately. Then the films were peeled from the substrates and dried at 40 °C for another 12 h to remove water. The thickness of these films is carefully controlled to about 15 μm. The volume fraction of f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs in nanocomposites is varied by 2.5%, 5%, 10%, and 15%, respectively.

2.5 Characterization

The morphology of f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs and the cross section of nanocomposites was inspected by scanning electron microscope (SEM, Nova NanoSEM 450, FEI, USA) and transmission electron

microscope (TEM, JEM-2010, JEOL, Japan). For dielectric measurement, Copper electrodes (12 mm in diameter) were deposited on both sides of the blends films. Dielectric constant and dielectric loss of the films were measured by using a Novocontrol Alpha-A high resolution dielectric analyzer (GmbH Concept 40) from 10^{-1} to 10^7 Hz under ambient temperature. Electric displacement-electric field (D-E) loops were measured using a Precision Multiferroic Materials Analyzer equipped (Radiant Inc.) at 100Hz.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The morphology of f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs and cross section of nanocomposites film with 15 vol. % f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs are shown in Figure 1. As shown in Figure 1a, the f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ exhibits good linear structure after modification. In addition, P(VDF-HFP) nanocomposites with 15 vol.% f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs shows homogeneous dispersion of f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs in cross sectional morphology, as seen in Figure 2b. This indicates that a decent compatibility exists between f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs and P(VDF-HFP) matrix.

Figure 1: SEM images of (a) f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs and (b) P(VDF-HFP)-based nanocomposite film with 15 vol. % f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs.

Figure 3a and 3b reveal the enhanced permittivity and varied dielectric loss of pure P(VDF-HFP) and nanocomposites films. With the content of f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs increasing, the dielectric constant of nanocomposites also enhance as the higher permittivity of BaTiO₃ NWs than that of P(VDF-HFP). At the volume fraction of 15% of f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs in nanocomposites, the dielectric constant of samples reached 24.3 at a frequency of 10 Hz, which is nearly twice times of P(VDF-HFP) matrix at the same frequency. As shown in Figure 2b, the dielectric loss at 10^4 to 10^6 Hz was reduced by adding f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs into P(VDF-HFP) matrix and the suppression effect increases with increasing the content of f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs. This can be ascribed to the suppression of chain relaxation of amorphous phase induced by rigid f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs. At low frequencies, a restrained loss tangent can be realized by incorporating 2.5 vol.% f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs into P(VDF-HFP) matrix, which reveals the good dispersion of f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs in P(VDF-HFP) matrix. This phenomenon can be attributed to the interfacial polarization, which was reported before.²⁴⁻²⁵ For the rest three nanocomposites films, the dielectric loss slightly varied at the frequencies between 10^2 and 10^3 Hz comparing with pure P(VDF-HFP), which further shows the good compatibility between f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs and P(VDF-HFP).

Figure 2: Dependences of (a) permittivity and (b) loss tangent on frequency for neat polymers and blends with different f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs compositions.

A modified Sawyer-Tower circuit was conducted to explore energy storage properties of these polymer films by measuring their D-E loops under unipolar electric field. As can be seen in Figure 3a, the electrical displacement of samples increase along with the increasing f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs content, which is consistent with the dielectric properties described above. Meanwhile, the remnant polarization is slightly increased due to the high spontaneous polarization of BaTiO₃. For P(VDF-HFP) nanocomposites with 2.5vol.% f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs, the max electric filed under D-E loops test is 550 MV/m, which is 1.1 times of pure P(VDF-HFP) and inspiring.

The energy density (U_e) can be calculated by the equation, $U_e = \int E dD$, whereas E is electric field, D implies the electrical displacement. Stored and discharged energy densities of every samples are shown in Figure 3b and 3c. Both the stored and discharged energy densities increase along with increasing the f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs content and electric field. For the composites films containing 2.5 vol.% and 5 vol.% f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs, the maximum stored energy density are 21.35 J·cm⁻³ and 22.58 J·cm⁻³, respectively, which is much higher than pure P(VDF-HFP) due to the enhancement of dielectric constant and maintained breakdown strength. Nevertheless, as the volume content increased to 10 vol.% and 15 vol.%, the stored energy densities started to decrease because of the reduced breakdown strength of nanocomposites. Similar results about discharged energy density can be seen in Figure 3c. The P(VDF-HFP) nanocomposite films containing 2.5 vol % f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs displays a discharged energy density of 12.68 J·cm⁻³ at 550 MV/m, which is more than three and a half times of BOPP at 600 MV/m.²⁰ At an electric field of 480MV/m, the nanocomposites film with 5 vol.% f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs exhibits an ultrahigh discharged energy density of 12.87 J·cm⁻³. In addition, at relatively low electric field of 340 MV/m, nanocomposites film with 15 vol.% f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs exhibits discharge energy density as high as 8.28 J·cm⁻³, which is approximately two times of pure P(VDF-HFP) (4.38 J·cm⁻³). These encouraging results show the great potential application of f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs in energy storage materials both at high and low electric field.

Figure 3: (a) D-E loops of pure P(VDF-HFP) and nanocomposites with different f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs compositions measured at 100Hz under unipolar electric field. (b) Stored energy density, (c) discharged energy density, and (d) efficiency of P(VDF-HFP) nanocomposites embedded with different volume fraction of f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs and pure P(VDF-HFP) films as a function of electric field.

Figure 3d summarizes the charge-discharge efficiencies of P(VDF-HFP) nanocomposites as a function of electric field. The efficiencies decreased while increasing the electric field. However, P(VDF-HFP) nanocomposites films with low volume fraction of f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs appear to match or exceed the efficiency of polymer matrix at electric field below 400MV/m, which further

indicates the great potential application of introducing modified BaTiO₃ NWs into polymer matrix to improve permittivity while maintain the charge-discharge efficiency. However, the dielectric loss under high electric field (>400MV/m) would probably restricts the potential application of as-prepared nanocomposites. Further research need to be conducted to address this problem.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, elastic polymer nanocomposites exhibiting high energy storage properties were implemented by introducing bio-inspired fluoro-polydopamine modified BaTiO₃ NWs into fluoropolymer. The nanocomposite film with 5 vol % f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs exhibits an ultrahigh discharged energy density of 12.87 J·cm⁻³ at an electric field of 480 MV/m, which is more than three and a half times of BOPP at 600 MV/m (3.56 J·cm⁻³). These brilliant energy storage abilities of as-prepared nanocomposite films appear to fair or exceed some reported advanced nanofillers-based polymer nanocomposites in the extent of 400-500 MV/m. The elaborate designed f-DOPA@BaTiO₃ NWs simultaneously increase permittivity and keep the breakdown strength of polymer matrix, which is critical for enhancing the energy storage capability of dielectric materials. However, energy loss at high electric field need more work to settle down because it is still a treadstone for the application of most dielectric films. Our strategy is simple and general compared with conventional redundant methods. As a consequence, this work paves an attractive way to fabricate polymer nanocomposites for high energy storage applications.

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